

STUDIES IN SESQUITERPENES. PART I. SYNTHESIS OF THE TRIMETHYL
ESTER OF $C_8H_{14}(CO_2H)_3$ -ACID OBTAINED FROM DIHYDROZINGIBERENE

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Condensation of diethyl α -methyl- α -(bromoacetyl)-glutarate with malonic ester, followed by hydrolysis and esterification, furnishes (V) which on treatment with zinc and bromoacetic ester gives the lactone (VI). On reduction of the above lactone, followed by esterification, (X), the trimethyl ester of $C_8H_{14}(CO_2H)_3$ acid, is obtained.

By the oxidative degradation of dihydrozingiberene, which was, in its turn, derived from zingiberene by reduction with sodium and alcohol, Ruzicka and Van Veen (*Annalen*, 1929, 468, 143) obtained a tricarboxylic acid which has been ascribed the constitution (IX). The present investigation deals with the synthesis of the trimethyl ester of the above acid.

A glance at the proposed structure (IX) of this acid reveals that it is a β -substituted adipic acid system. Its synthesis has been accomplished following the usual method for the building of such systems, namely Reformatsky's reaction between ethyl bromoacetate and the corresponding keto-ester, followed by reduction. Ethyl α -acetylglutarate (I), the starting material for the preparation of the keto-ester (V), is obtained in satisfactory yield in the usual way by the condensation of ethyl β -chloropropionate with ethyl sodio-acetoacetate in benzene. Methylation of ethyl α -acetylglutarate with sodium (pulverised) and methyl iodide proceeds smoothly to give ethyl α -methyl- α -acetylglutarate (II). The ω -bromo derivative (III) is obtained by the bromination of (II), following the conditions laid down by Conrad and Kreichgauer (*Ber.*, 1897, 30, 856) for the bromination of ethyl dimethylacetoacetate, that is, by the simple addition of bromine in the cold to ethyl α -methyl- α -acetylglutarate (II), when γ -bromo- α -methyl- α -(ethyl β -propionate)-acetoacetate (III) is obtained as a yellowish oil, which decomposes on distillation presumably with the formation of a keto- γ -lactone through the elimination of ethyl bromide from the molecule (*cf.* Conrad and Kreichgauer, *loc. cit.*). The bromo derivative reacts readily and smoothly with ethyl sodiomalonate in benzene to give diethyl $\alpha\delta$ -dicarboxy- γ -keto- δ -methylsuberate (IV) in excellent yield (*cf.* Conrad and Kreichgauer, *loc. cit.*). Few attempts seem to have been reported in the literature to condense the γ -bromo derivatives of ethyl-disubstituted acetoacetate with sodiomalonic ester, although by this means many compounds could be synthetically prepared, the formation of which by other means would have been long and tedious.

The tetracarboxylic ester (IV) is hydrolysed smoothly with concentrated hydrochloric acid. The keto-acid, thus obtained as a thick liquid, is esterified with alcohol and sulphuric acid to give ethyl γ -keto- δ -methylsuberate (V). This keto-diester is then subjected to Reformatsky's reaction with zinc and ethyl bromoacetate, when a lactone (VI) is obtained. Although it is immaterial for our purpose whether this lactone is a γ - or a δ -lactone, the former is preferred since the substance is insoluble in 5% alkali.

The lactone ring is opened up with phosphorus pentabromide, followed by the treatment of the bromo-acid-bromide with ethyl alcohol. The crude bromo-ester (VII) on being reduced with zinc dust and acetic acid gives the triethyl ester of the tricarboxylic acid (IX). The above lactone is also reduced by red phosphorus and hydriodic acid. The crude acid, thus obtained, could not be solidified, and on esterification with methyl alcohol and sulphuric acid gives the trimethyl ester (X) of the acid (IX). The boiling point of the trimethyl ester agrees well with that of the ester obtained by Ruzicka and Van Veen (*loc. cit.*) by the oxidative degradation of dihydrozingiberene. An attempt has been made to obtain the acid in a crystalline form by hydrolysing the above ester but without success.

It will not be out of place to mention another attempt towards the synthesis of the tricarboxylic acid (IX) by a somewhat different route. Ethyl β -(*sec.*-isooctyl)-adipate (XIV) was obtained by subjecting ethyl δ -isohexylhomolaevulate (XI) to Reformatsky's reaction with zinc and ethyl bromoacetate, followed by reduction of the resulting lactone by opening up the lactone ring with phosphorus pentabromide and alcohol, and subsequent treatment with zinc dust and acetic acid.

The preparation of ethyl δ -isohexylhomolaevulate (XI) has been described in a separate communication (*this issue*). It will be evident that if the isopropyl group at the end of the chain in (XIV) be eliminated through oxidation according to the well known method of Windaus (*Z. physiol. Chem.*, 1921, 117, 146; 1923, 126, 277), the tricarboxylic acid (IX) will be obtained. Similar oxidations have been reported in the literature where an isopropyl group is attacked through oxidation with chromic acid or potassium permanganate (Lawrence, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1899, 75, 529; Linstead and Rydon, *ibid.*, 1933, 585; Rydon, *ibid.*, 1936, 594).

The present scheme of work may be represented thus:

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Diethyl α -Methyl- α -(bromoacetyl)-glutarate (III).—Diethyl α -acetylglutarate (I, 50 g.) (obtained by condensation of ethyl β -chloropropionate with ethyl sodioacetoacetate) was slowly added to sodium dust (5 g.), suspended in 250 c. c. of dry benzene and left overnight. To the sodio-salt, thus formed, 42 g. (1.5 mol.) of methyl iodide were added and the whole refluxed for 10 hours on the water-bath. Water was added to the cooled reaction mixture and the separated benzene layer was washed and dried. After the removal of the solvent 40 g. of diethyl α -acetyl- α -methylglutarate (II), b. p. 136-38°/6.5 mm. were obtained (the product does not respond to colour reaction with alcoholic ferric chloride).

To the above ester (II, 50 g.), cooled in ice-water, was added dropwise bromine (11 c.c., slight excess of 1 mol.). At first there was observed a lag in the absorption of bromine but once it started, bromine was taken up instantaneously. During the later part of the addition hydrobromic acid was evolved. After the addition of bromine was complete, the reaction mixture was allowed to stand for half-an-hour in the ice-bath and then hydrobromic acid was driven off in the water pump. To assure complete removal of hydrobromic acid the flask was subjected to a higher vacuum (6 mm.) for 1 hour, when a rather thick amber-coloured liquid was obtained.

Diethyl α , δ -Dicarboethoxy- γ -keto- δ -methylsuberate (IV).—Sodium dust (6 g.) under dry benzene (150 c. c.) was cooled in ice-water and diethyl malonate (50 g.) added slowly. The reaction mixture was kept overnight and to this the above crude bromo-ester (III) was added in the cold with shaking and the whole refluxed for 16 hours. The benzene layer, separated after the addition of water to the cooled reaction mixture, was washed with water and dried over calcium chloride. After removal of the solvent the residue was distilled in vacuum, when 72 g. of a thick liquid boiling at 235-36°/5 mm. were obtained. A slight decomposition was observed during distillation. (Found: C, 56.53 ; H, 7.08. $C_{16}H_{20}O_6$ requires C, 56.7 ; H, 7.46 per cent).

Diethyl γ -Keto- δ -methylsuberate (V).—The above tetracarboxylic ester (IV, 72 g.) was refluxed with 400 c. c. of concentrated hydrochloric acid for 36 hours after which the cooled solution was extracted thrice with ether. The combined ether extract was dried (Na_2SO_4) and the solvent removed. The residue was dried in vacuum and refluxed with a mixture of 150 c. c. of dry alcohol and 15 c. c. of sulphuric acid (d 1.84) for 20 hours. After dilution with cold water the solution was extracted with ether, the ethereal layer washed with sodium bicarbonate solution, water and dried ($CaCl_2$). The residue left after the removal of the solvent was distilled in *vacuo* and a colourless, mobile liquid was obtained, b. p. 160-81°/7mm., yield 25 g. (Found: C, 60.2 ; H, 8.47. $C_{12}H_{12}O_5$ requires C, 60.46 ; H, 8.52 per cent).

Diethyl Ester of the Lactone of γ -Hydroxy- γ -(acetic acid)- δ -methylsuberic Acid (VI).—The keto-diester (V, 25 g.), dissolved in 50 c. c. of benzene was subjected to Reformatsky's reaction with ethyl bromoacetate (8 c. c.) and zinc wool (15 g.) (activated before use by washing it with dilute hydrochloric acid, water and acetone, and dried in vacuum). A few crystals of iodine were added and heated on the water-bath. Within 5 to 6 minutes the colour of iodine disappeared and the solution became turbid and within 15 minutes vigorous reaction took place. After the initial vigour of the reaction had subsided the heating was continued for 1 hour and a fresh addition of 8 c. c. of ethyl bromoacetate, 15 g. of zinc wool (activated) and a few crystals of iodine was made and refluxing continued for 2 hours more. The reaction mixture was shaken from time to time in order to free the surface of zinc from the adhering mass of zinc complex formed in the reaction. It was then cooled and decomposed with acetic acid and methanol, and after considerable dilution with water the benzene layer was taken up and washed with dilute ammonia several times until the ammoniacal layer was almost colourless. Finally the benzene layer was washed with water and dried ($CaCl_2$). The residue, after the removal of benzene, was distilled in vacuum when 16 g. of the lactone (VI) was obtained, b. p. 186°/5 mm. (Found: C, 59.7 ; H, 7.8. $C_{13}H_{14}O_5$ requires C, 60.0 ; H, 8.0 per cent).

Diethyl γ -(Ethyl acetate)- δ -methylsuberate (VIII).—The lactonic ester (VI, 16 g.) was treated in the cold with PBr_3 (30 g.) and allowed to stand overnight, when practically the whole of the PBr_3 went into solution. The thick red solution was poured into 50 c. c. of well cooled absolute alcohol when a vigorous reaction took place. The solution was afterwards refluxed on the water-bath for half-an-hour, cooled and diluted with cold water, and the heavy layer extracted with ether. The ethereal layer was washed with sodium bicarbonate solution and water, and dried ($CaCl_2$). After the evaporation of

the solvent the residue was dried in *vacuo* and dissolved in 250 c.c. of glacial acetic acid. To this solution was added with shaking zinc dust (40 g.) in small portions during 2 hours and then the reaction mixture was refluxed on a sand-bath for 24 hours. The acetic acid solution was separated from the zinc and cooled, and the major portion of the acetic acid was neutralised with caustic soda solution. The layer, which separated, was extracted with ether, the ethereal layer washed with sodium carbonate solution, water and dried. The residue left after the evaporation of the ether came over at 187-88°/6 mm. (Found: C, 61.4; H, 8.86. $C_{17}H_{28}O_8$ requires C, 61.8; H, 9.1 per cent).

Dimethyl γ -(Methyl acetate)- δ -methylsebacate (X).—The lactonic diester (VI, 2 g.) was refluxed with an excess of red phosphorus and hydriodic acid (*d* 1.7) for a prolonged period (48 hours). The reaction mixture was diluted, filtered and the filter paper well washed with ether which was added to the filtrate. The ethereal layer was separated and the aqueous layer extracted once more with ether. The combined ether extract was washed with water and dried over sodium sulphate. On removal of the solvent an uncrystallisable resinous mass was left as a residue. The crude product after being dried in *vacuo* was esterified by refluxing with dry methyl alcohol (25 c.c.) and sulphuric acid (4 c.c., *d* 1.84) for 24 hours. After working up in the usual manner, the trimethyl ester (X) was obtained, b.p. 182°/6 mm. (Lit. b.p. 145-150°/0.3 mm.). (Found: C, 57.94; H, 8.16. $C_{14}H_{24}O_4$ requires C, 58.33; H, 8.33 per cent).

γ -sec.-isoOctyl γ -(Ethyl acetate)- γ -butyrolactone (XII).—Ethyl δ -isohexylhomolaevalate (XI, 10 g.) in dry benzene (30 c.c.) was subjected to Reformatsky's reaction with activated zinc wool (5 g.), 3.5 c.c. of ethyl bromoacetate and a crystal or two of iodine according to the procedure described above. Fresh addition of 5 g. of zinc wool and 3.5 c.c. of ethyl bromoacetate and a dry crystal of iodine was made after an hour and refluxing continued for 2 hours more. After cooling, the complex was decomposed with acetic acid and methanol and after dilution with water, extracted with ether. The ether-benzene solution was washed several times with dilute ammonia until the alkaline solution ceased to be coloured, and then with water and dried ($CaCl_2$). After evaporation of ether and benzene from the solution, the residue came over in vacuum at 168°/4 mm., yield 4.5 g. (Found: C, 67.2; H, 9.8. $C_{18}H_{28}O_4$ requires C, 67.6; H, 9.85 per cent).

Diethyl β -sec.-isoOctyladipate (XIII).—The above lactonic ester (4 g.) was treated with PBr_3 (7 g.) according to the procedure described before and the resulting bromo-acid-bromide was treated with 25 c.c. of cooled alcohol and the solution refluxed for 15 minutes. After dilution in the cold with water, a heavy layer settled at the bottom. The mixture was extracted with ether and the ethereal layer washed with $NaHCO_3$ solution and water. After drying with $CaCl_2$ the solvent was removed and the residue dried in vacuum.

The crude bromo-ester, thus obtained, was dissolved in 50 c.c. of acetic acid and to this 8 g. of zinc dust added in portions during half-an-hour and the whole refluxed on a sand-bath for 16 hours. After neutralisation of almost 2/3 of the acetic acid with caustic soda solution, the extraction was effected with ether, the ethereal layer washed with sodium carbonate solution and water, and dried. The residue left after the evaporation of the solvent was distilled when a halogen-free liquid came over at

159-80°/4 mm. (Found : C, 68.3 ; H, 9.87. $C_{11}H_{14}O_4$ requires C, 68.78 ; H, 10.8 per cent).

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